

A Preliminary Floristic Exploration in Penna Ahobilam Sacred Grove, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh State

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Abstract

Background Sacred groves in Andhra Pradesh are known as Pavithravanas. A total number of 730 sacred groves have been documented till date. These Pavithravanas or sacred groves are dedicated to various local deities and also to Hindu gods and goddesses. Some of the deities to whom the sacred groves are dedicated are Shiva, Rudrakoteswara, Hanuman, Saraswathi, Thimmaraya Swamy, Gangamma, Nagadevatha, Chennakesava, Narasimha and Akkamma (WWF Andhra Pradesh, 1996). **Results** During study of sacred grove of Andhra Pradesh State, India various field trips were conducted and were GIS Photographic from various natural populations during the period 2018-2026. Collected Sacred groves identifications activities data and plants specimens collected flowering or fruiting seasons. Specimens critically observed and identified. In the present study, a total of 378 wild and naturalized species were recorded from Penna Ahobilam Sacred Grove, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh. These 378 wild and naturalized species belong to 220 genera and 54 families. Of the 378 wild and naturalized species, 49 trees, 56 shrubs; 235 herbs; 38 Climbers. **Conclusion** Sacred groves in Andhra Pradesh are deteriorating at an alarming rate due to changes in religious beliefs and developmental pressure. Many temples associated with sacred groves have been modernized by removing the vegetation. Some of the species commonly found in the sacred groves of Andhra Pradesh are black plum, tamarind, mango, jackfruit, neem, beechwood and pipal. Some of the species have unique abilities such as nitrogen fixation etc. Such species are variously known as keystone species or functional groups.

Keywords: *Pampanur, Pavithranams, Primary Data Collections, Sacred Grove.*

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Introduction

The sacred groves are important repositories of floral and faunal diversity that have been conserved by local communities in a sustainable manner. They are often the last refuge of endemic species in the geographical region. The role of cultural and spiritual values is crucial to nature conservation. In India, the sacred groves are still in the process of being documented. There are 13,270 sacred groves that are found to intact. Out of this only 138 hectares comprise of totally undisturbed vegetation and about 3188 hectares have an open canopy. However, initial studies indicate that the number of sacred groves in the country may be as high as 100,000 to 150,000 (Malhotra, 1998). The total area under sacred groves in India has been estimated to be 33,000 hectares which comes to 0.01 percent of the total area of the country. However, the actual area could be as high as 42000 hectares considering the 4,445 sacred groves reported so far (Gokhale et al. 1998). However, in contrast to the above facts, C.P.R. Environmental Education Centre has so far documented a total of 10,377 sacred groves which have been authenticated. In India, over 1 million Sacred Forests and 100,000 to 150,000 sacred groves exist. This spiritual belief is very similar to the mechanism of a healthy ecosystem.

Many scientists believe that traditions and faiths like these are essential to encourage biodiversity conservation efforts (Malhotra et al. 1998). A document of (MAB 1995) has described the sacred groves present in Ghana, Senegal, and Sumatra. Various sacred sites associated with rich vegetation in Bangladesh were reported by (Hussain 1998). All forms of vegetation in the groves are supposed to be under the protection of reigning deity of that grove, and the removal of even a small twig is a taboo (Vartak and Gadgil 1973). Collection and removal of any material from the sacred groves is prohibited (Khan et al. 1987; Khiewtam and Ramakrishnan 1989). Sacred groves are found all over India especially in those regions where indigenous communities inhabit. Traced the historical link of sacred groves with the pre-agricultural, hunting and gathering stage, before human being had settled down to raise livestock or till land (Gadgil and Vartak 1976, 1981 a,b). Most of the sacred groves reported from India are in the Western Ghats, North Eastern India and Central India (Gadgil and Vartak 1976; Burman 1992; Rodgers 1994; Balasuramanyam and Induchoodan 1996; Tripathi 2006; Khumbongmayum et al. 2005). In India sacred groves are found mainly in tribal dominated areas and known by different names in ethnic terms (Bhakat 1990) such as Sarna or Dev in Madhya Pradesh, Devrai or Deovani in Maharashtra, Sarnas in Bihar, Oran's in Rajasthan, Devaravana or Devarakadu in Karnataka, Sarpakavu and Kavuvu in Tamil Nadu and Kerala, Dev van in Himachal Pradesh, Law Lyngdoh or Law Kyntang etc. in Meghalaya, Sarana or Jaherthan in Jharkhand and Laiumang in Manipur.

Materials and Methods

During study of sacred grove of Andhra Pradesh State, India various field trips were conducted and were vouched from various natural populations during the period 2018-2026. Collected Sacred groves identifications activities data and plants photographic data collected flowering or fruiting seasons. Plants critically observed and identified. Based on the information, plants were identified with the help of local floras and confirmed by comparing with authenticated specimens in Deccan Regional Centre, BSI, Hyderabad, Coimbatore and central National herbarium (CAL), Calcutta. The state of Andhra Pradesh, alone, has over 500 sacred groves (Anon. 1996), Locally known as Pavithravanalu (Rao et al. 2001; Sunitha and Rao 1999) studied the characteristics and distribution of the flora of the sacred groves in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. (Prasad Varma et. al. 2023) reported a total of 67 species 57 genera and 32 families in Bodakondamma sacred grove, Eastern Ghats, Visakhapatnam District. Biodiversity of Sacred groves is preserved in mostly undisturbed condition probably due to certain taboos and religious beliefs (Lakshmi Narayana and Venkaiah 1998). The Local people of each sacred grove in general also believe

that their livelihood, security and cultural existence are complementary to the blessings of their deity. Perusal of related published literature (Gamble 1915; Gamble and Fischer 1915; Gibbs 1974; Halbar 1986; Hooker 1984; Hooker 1872-1897; Jain 1964; Jain and Rao 1977; Jain 1981; Jain 1964; Jain 1981; Kirtikar and Boser 1933; Nadkarni 1976; Pullaiah and Yasodamma 1989; Pullaiah and Chennaiah 1997; Rao and Sree Ramulu 1986; Reddy et al. 1986; Subba Rao and Kumari 2002-2008) for the taxonomic confirmation.

Penna Ahobilam is situated approximately 12 km from Uravakonda and 36 km from Anantapur town in Andhra Pradesh. The area lies within the semi-arid zone of the Deccan Plateau and experiences hot summers with moderate seasonal rainfall. The vegetation is predominantly tropical dry deciduous scrub mixed with thorny species and scattered tree growth.

The sacred grove surrounding the temple complex represents a remnant natural vegetation patch protected through religious beliefs and traditional practices. Rocky hills, shallow soils, seasonal streams, and sacred water sources create diverse microhabitats supporting various herbs, shrubs, climbers, and trees. The vegetation of Penna Ahobilam Sacred Grove consists mainly of tropical dry deciduous and scrub forest elements. Commonly observed plant species may include: *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. *Ficus religiosa* L., *Ficus benghalensis* L., *Albizia amara* (Roxb.) Boivin, *Tamarindus indica* L., *Pongamia pinnata* (L.) Pierre, *Syzygium cumini* (L.) Skeels, *Wrightia tinctoria* R.Br., *Chloroxylon swietenia* DC.

Field explorations were conducted during different seasons to record plant diversity in the sacred grove. Plant specimens were collected during flowering and fruiting periods for proper identification. Standard floras and taxonomic literature were used for species authentication. Photographic documentation and ecological observations were also carried out during the survey. Similar floristic approaches have been adopted in sacred grove studies across Andhra Pradesh.

Penna Ahobilam Sacred Grove represents an ecologically and culturally significant biodiversity conservation site in the semi-arid landscapes of Andhra Pradesh. The grove harbors valuable medicinal and native plant species preserved through traditional religious beliefs. Preliminary floristic exploration highlights the importance of sacred groves as refugia for biodiversity conservation and emphasizes the need for sustainable management and ecological restoration for future generations.

Results and Discussions

In the present study, a total a total of 378 wild and naturalized species were recorded from Penna Ahobilam Sacred Grove, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh. These 378 wild and naturalized species belong to 220 genera and 54 families. Of the 378 wild and naturalized species, 49 trees, 56 shrubs; 235 herbs; 38 Climbers.

Sacred groves are ecologically, culturally, and spiritually significant. They serve as biodiversity hotspots, conserving rare and endemic species of flora and fauna. Ecologically, they act as carbon sinks, regulate microclimates, and prevent soil erosion. Culturally, they are integral to local traditions, often protected through religious beliefs, rituals, and taboos. They also support traditional knowledge systems, including medicinal plant usage. Despite their importance, sacred groves face threats like deforestation and urbanization, highlighting the need for conservation efforts that integrate local communities and modern ecological strategies. Floristic exploration of sacred groves is a vital activity for understanding and conserving plant biodiversity.

Conclusion

Sacred groves are unique ecosystems, often serving as reservoirs of rare, endemic, and medicinal plant species. Here are the key reasons why floristic exploration is crucial. Sacred groves are biodiversity

hotspots. Floristic exploration helps identify and catalogue plant species, including those that are rare, endangered, or have limited geographical distribution. Trees and plants in sacred groves play a significant role in carbon capture. Identifying dominant species helps estimate their carbon storage potential. Plants in sacred groves often exhibit resilience to climate extremes. Exploring their floristic composition can provide insights into climate-adaptive species. Floristic surveys can reveal the impact of deforestation, grazing, and urbanization on plant diversity, emphasizing the need for conservation. Identifying invasive plant species helps manage threats to native flora. Floristic exploration in sacred groves is not just a scientific endeavour but also a conservation imperative. It integrates traditional knowledge with modern science, ensuring that these ancient ecological sanctuaries continue to thrive and provide their invaluable benefits to nature and society.

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Author Contribution

Corresponding authors Field data collections, documentation work, specimens' identifications and field photos taken and photo plates prepared. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Appendix

S. No	Name of the Species	Families	Habit
1	<i>Abelmoschus ficulneus</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Malvaceae	H
2	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Fabaceae	C
3	<i>Abutilon hirtum</i> (Lam.) Sweet	Malvaceae	S
4	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Malvaceae	S
5	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f.) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
6	<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Rottler) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
7	<i>Acacia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Fabaceae	T
8	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Delile	Fabaceae	T
9	<i>Acacia torta</i> (Roxb.) Craib	Fabaceae	S
10	<i>Acalypha alnifolia</i> Klein ex Willd.	Euphorbiaceae	S
11	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	H
12	<i>Acalypha lanceolata</i> Willd.	Euphorbiaceae	H
13	<i>Acalypha malabarica</i> Müll.Arg	Euphorbiaceae	H
14	<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC	Asteraceae	H
15	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
16	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	Rutaceae	T
17	<i>Aerva javanica</i> (Burm.f.) Juss. ex Schult.	Amaranthaceae	H
18	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Amaranthaceae	H
19	<i>Aeschynomene indica</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
20	<i>Alangium salviifolium</i> (L.f.) Wangerin	Cornaceae	S
21	<i>Albizia amara</i> (Roxb.) B.Boivin	Fabaceae	T
22	<i>Allmania nodiflora</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Wight	Amaranthaceae	H
23	<i>Alloteropsis cimicina</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
24	<i>Alternanthera pungens</i> Kunth	Amaranthaceae	H
25	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	Amaranthaceae	H
26	<i>Alysicarpus bupleurifolius</i> (L.) DC	Fabaceae	H
27	<i>Alysicarpus hamosus</i> Edgew.	Fabaceae	H
28	<i>Alysicarpus monilifer</i> (L.) DC	Fabaceae	H

29	<i>Alysicarpus vaginalis</i> (L.) DC	Fabaceae	H
30	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
31	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i>	Amaranthaceae	H
32	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	H
33	<i>Andrographis serpyllifolia</i> (Rottl. ex Vahl.) Wt.	Acanthaceae	H
34	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
35	<i>Anisochilus carnosus</i> (L.f.) Wall.	Lamiaceae	H
36	<i>Anisomeles indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Lamiaceae	H
37	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Sims	Lamiaceae	H
38	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Annonaceae	T
39	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wall. ex Guillem. & Perr.	Combretaceae	T
40	<i>Apluda mutica</i> L.	Poaceae	H
41	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	H
42	<i>Argyreia cymosa</i> Sweet	Convolvulaceae	C
43	<i>Aristida adscensionis</i> L.	Poaceae	H
44	<i>Aristida setacea</i> Retz.	Poaceae	H
45	<i>Aristolochia bracteata</i>	Aristolochiaceae	H
46	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Aristolochiaceae	Twin
47	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Asparagaceae	C
48	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss	Meliaceae	T
49	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Wettst.	Plantaginaceae	H
50	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i> (L.) Delile	Zygophyllaceae	T
51	<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	Acanthaceae	S
52	<i>Barleria longiflora</i> L.f.	Acanthaceae	S
53	<i>Barleria noctiflora</i> L.f.	Acanthaceae	S
54	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	Acanthaceae	S
55	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> L.	Fabaceae	T
56	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Fabaceae	T
57	<i>Bauhinia tomentosa</i> L.	Fabaceae	T
58	<i>Benkara malabarica</i> (Lam.) Tirveng	Rubiaceae	S
59	<i>Blainvillea acmella</i> (L.) Philipson	Asteraceae	H
60	<i>Blepharis integrifolia</i> (L.f.) E.Mey. & Drège ex Schinz	Acanthaceae	H
61	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> (L.) B.Heyne ex Roth	Acanthaceae	H
62	<i>Blumea eriantha</i> DC	Asteraceae	H
63	<i>Blumea obliqua</i> (L.) Druce	Asteraceae	H
64	<i>Boerhavia chinensis</i> (L.) Rottb	Nyctaginaceae	H
65	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	H
66	<i>Boerhavia erecta</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	H
67	<i>Bothriochloa pertusa</i> (L.) A.Camus	Poaceae	H
68	<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
69	<i>Brachiaria eruciformis</i> (Sm.) Griseb.	Poaceae	H
70	<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
71	<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
72	<i>Brachiaria reptans</i> (L.) C.A.Gardner & C.E.Hubb.	Poaceae	H
73	<i>Bridelia montana</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Phyllanthaceae	T
74	<i>Bulbostylis barbata</i> (Rottb.) C.B.Clarke	Cyperaceae	C
75	<i>Cadaba fruticosa</i> (L.) Druce	Capparaceae	S
76	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand.	Apocyanaceae	S
77	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton) Dryand.	Apocyanaceae	S
78	<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forssk.) Edgew	Capparaceae	S
79	<i>Capparis floribunda</i> Lepr. ex Walp	Capparaceae	S
80	<i>Capparis sepiaria</i> L	Capparaceae	S
81	<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> L	Capparaceae	S
82	<i>Caralluma adscendens</i> (Roxb.) Haw.	Apocyanaceae	H
83	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L	Sapindaceae	C
84	<i>Carissa carandas</i> L.	Apocyanaceae	S

85	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Fabaceae	T
86	<i>Cassytha filiformis</i> L.	Lauraceae	C
87	<i>Catharanthus pusillus</i> (Murray) G.Don	Apocyanaceae	H
88	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i> (Thunb.) Tirveng.	Rubiaceae	S
89	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
90	<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i> L.	Poaceae	H
91	<i>Chamaecrista absus</i> (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	Fabaceae	H
92	<i>Chamaecrista pumila</i> (Lam.) K.Larsen	Fabaceae	H
93	<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	Poaceae	H
94	<i>Chrozophora rottleri</i> (Geiseler) A.Juss. ex Spreng	Euphorbiaceae	H
95	<i>Chrysopogon fulvus</i> (Spreng.) Chiov.	Poaceae	H
96	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Menispermaceae	V
97	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Vitaceae	V
98	<i>Cissus vitiginea</i> L.	Vitaceae	C
99	<i>Cleome aspera</i> J.Koenig ex DC.	Cleomaceae	H
100	<i>Cleome felina</i> L.f.	Cleomaceae	H
101	<i>Cleome gynandra</i> L.	Cleomaceae	H
102	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Cleomaceae	H
103	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Fabaceae	C
104	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt	Cucurbitaceae	C
105	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L.) W.Theob.	Menispermaceae	C
106	<i>Coldenia procumbens</i> L.	Boraginaceae	H
107	<i>Combretum albidum</i> G.Don	Combretaceae	S
108	<i>Commelina attenuata</i> K.D.Koenig ex Vahl	Commelinaceae	H
109	<i>Commelina badamica</i>	Commelinaceae	h
110	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Commelinaceae	H
111	<i>Commelina clavata</i> C.B.Clarke	Commelinaceae	H
112	<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm.f.	Commelinaceae	H
113	<i>Commelina erecta</i> L.	Commelinaceae	H
114	<i>Corallocarpus epigaeus</i> (Rottler) Hook.f.	Cucurbitaceae	C
115	<i>Corchorus aestuans</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
116	<i>Corchorus fascicularis</i> Lam	Malvaceae	S
117	<i>Corchorus trilocularis</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
118	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G.Forst.	Boraginaceae	T
119	<i>Crotalaria albida</i> Roth	Fabaceae	H
120	<i>Crotalaria angulata</i> Mill	Fabaceae	H
121	<i>Crotalaria bifaria</i> L.f.	Fabaceae	H
122	<i>Crotalaria hebecarpa</i> (DC.) Rudd	Fabaceae	H
123	<i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
124	<i>Crotalaria medicaginea</i> Lam	Fabaceae	H
125	<i>Crotalaria ramosissima</i> Roxb	Fabaceae	H
126	<i>Crotalaria retusa</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
127	<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i> L.	Fabaceae	H
128	<i>Croton bonplandianus</i> Baill.	Euphorbiaceae	H
129	<i>Cryptostegia grandiflora</i> Roxb. ex R.Br.	Apocyanaceae	C
130	<i>Ctenolepis garcini</i> (L.) C.B.Clarke	Cucurbitaceae	C
131	<i>Cuscuta chinensis</i> Lam.	Convolvulaceae	C
132	<i>Cyanotis axillaris</i> (L.) D.Don ex Sweet	Commelinaceae	H
133	<i>Cyanotis fasciculata</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Schult. & Schult.f.	Commelinaceae	H
134	<i>Cyanotis tuberosa</i> (Roxb.) Schult. & Schult.f.	Commelinaceae	H
135	<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H.Rob	Asteraceae	H
136	<i>Cymbopogon caesius</i> (Hook. & Arn.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
137	<i>Cymbopogon coloratus</i> (Hook.f.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
138	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	H
139	<i>Cyperus laevigatus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	H
140	<i>Cyperus niveus</i> Retzius	Cyperaceae	H
141	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	H

142	<i>Cyperus rubicundus</i> Vahl	Cyperaceae	H
143	<i>Cyphostemma setosum</i> (Roxb.) Alston	Vitaceae	C
144	<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd	Poaceae	H
145	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> Roxb	Fabaceae	T
146	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> DC.	Fabaceae	T
147	<i>Datura innoxia</i> Mill.	Solanaceae	S
148	<i>Deccania pubescens</i> (Roth) Tirveng.	Rubiaceae	T
149	<i>Derris scandens</i>	Fabaceae	S
150	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	H
151	<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	H
152	<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	Poaceae	H
153	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Fabaceae	S
154	<i>Dicliptera paniculata</i> (Forssk.) I.Darbysh	Acanthaceae	H
155	<i>Dicoma tomentosa</i> Cass.	Asteraceae	H
156	<i>Digera muricata</i> (L.) Mart.	Amaranthaceae	H
157	<i>Digitaria bicornis</i> (Lam.) Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
158	<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koeler	Poaceae	H
159	<i>Digitaria tomentosa</i> (J.Koenig ex Rottler) Henrard	Poaceae	H
160	<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (Vahl) Panz.	Poaceae	H
161	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C.Jeffrey	Cucurbitaceae	C
162	<i>Dipteracanthus prostratus</i> (Poir.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
163	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (L.) Jacq.	Sapindaceae	S
164	<i>Dolichandrone falcata</i> (Wall. ex DC.) Seem	Bignoniaceae	T
165	<i>Dregea volubilis</i> (L.f.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	Apocyanaceae	C
166	<i>Drimia indica</i> (Roxb.) Jessop	Asparagaceae	H
167	<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	H
168	<i>Echinops echinatus</i> Roxb	Asteraceae	H
169	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	H
170	<i>Ehretia aspera</i> Willd.	Boraginaceae	T
171	<i>Ehretia microphylla</i>	Boraginaceae	S
172	<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Poaceae	H
173	<i>Elytraria acaulis</i> (L.f.) Lindau	Acanthaceae	H
174	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.) DC. ex DC.	Asteraceae	H
175	<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Poir. ex Lam.) A.Raynal	Gentianaceae	H
176	<i>Enteropogon dolichostachyus</i> (Lag.) Keng	Poaceae	H
177	<i>Eragrostiella bifaria</i> (Vahl) Bor	Poaceae	H
178	<i>Eragrostiella brachyphylla</i> (Stapf) Bor	Poaceae	H
179	<i>Eragrostis amabilis</i> (L.) Wight & Arn	Poaceae	H
180	<i>Eragrostis atrovirens</i> (Desf.) Trin. ex Steud.	Poaceae	H
181	<i>Eragrostis japonica</i> (Thunb.) Trin	Poaceae	H
182	<i>Eragrostis viscosa</i> (Retz.) Trin.	Poaceae	H
183	<i>Eriochloa procera</i> (Retz.) C.E.Hubb.	Poaceae	H
184	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	T
185	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	H
186	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	H
187	<i>Euphorbia indica</i> Lam.	Euphorbiaceae	H
188	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L.) L.	Convolvulaceae	H
189	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Moraceae	T
190	<i>Ficus hispida</i> L.f.	Moraceae	T
191	<i>Ficus mollis</i> Vahl	Moraceae	T
192	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Moraceae	T
193	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	T
194	<i>Flueggea leucopyrus</i> Willd.	Phyllanthaceae	S
195	<i>Gisekia pharnaceoides</i> L.	Gisekiaceae	H
196	<i>Glinus oppositifolius</i>	Molluginaceae	H
197	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Colchicaceae	C
198	<i>Glossocardia bosvallia</i> (L.f.) DC	Asteraceae	H

199	<i>Gmelina asiatica</i> L.	Lamiaceae	T
200	<i>Gomphrena serrata</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	H
201	<i>Grewia bracteata</i> Roth	Malvaceae	S
202	<i>Grewia orbiculata</i> Rottler	Malvaceae	T
203	<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forssk.) Fiori	Malvaceae	S
204	<i>Grewia villosa</i> Willd	Malvaceae	S
205	<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> (Retz.) R.Br. ex Sm.	Apocyanaceae	C
206	<i>Gymnosporia emarginata</i> (Willd.) Thwaites	Celastraceae	S
207	<i>Gyrocarpus americanus</i> Jacq.	Hernandiaceae	T
208	<i>Hardwickia binata</i> Roxb	Fabaceae	T
209	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Malvaceae	T
210	<i>Heliotropium bracteatum</i> R.Br.	Boraginaceae	H
211	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.	Boraginaceae	H
212	<i>Heliotropium strigosum</i> Willd.	Boraginaceae	H
213	<i>Heliotropium zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) Lam.	Boraginaceae	H
214	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Schult.	Apocyanaceae	H
215	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
216	<i>Hibiscus micranthus</i> L.f.	Malvaceae	H
217	<i>Hibiscus vitifolius</i> L.	Malvaceae	S
218	<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit	Lamiaceae	H
219	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i> (L.) W.T.Aiton	Apocyanaceae	S
220	<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i> L.	Fabaceae	S
221	<i>Indigofera linnaei</i> Ali	Fabaceae	H
222	<i>Indigofera prostrata</i> Willd.	Fabaceae	H
223	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.	Fabaceae	S
224	<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i> L.	Fabaceae	S
225	<i>Indigofera trita</i> L.f.	Fabaceae	S
226	<i>Indoneesiella echioides</i> (L.) Sreem.	Acanthaceae	H
227	<i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	C
228	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	Convolvulaceae	C
229	<i>Ipomoea staphylina</i> Roem. & Schult.	Convolvulaceae	c
230	<i>Iseilema laxum</i> Hack.	Poaceae	H
231	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	S
232	<i>Justicia glauca</i> Rottler	Acanthaceae	H
233	<i>Justicia procumbens</i> L.	Acanthaceae	H
234	<i>Kohautia aspera</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Bremek	Rubiaceae	H
235	<i>Kyllinga bulbosa</i> P.Beauv.	Cyperaceae	H
236	<i>Kyllinga nemoralis</i> (J.R.Forst. & G.Forst.) Dandy ex Hutch. & Dalziel	Cyperaceae	H
237	<i>Lagascea mollis</i> Cav.	Asteraceae	H
238	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.) Merr	Anacardiaceae	T
239	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Verbenaceae	S
240	<i>Ledebouria revoluta</i> (L.f.) Jessop	Asparagaceae	H
241	<i>Leonotis nepetifolia</i> (L.) R.Br.	Lamiaceae	H
242	<i>Lepidagathis cristata</i> Willd.	Acanthaceae	H
243	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	Lamiaceae	H
244	<i>Leucas diffusa</i> Benth	Lamiaceae	H
245	<i>Limonia acidissima</i> Groff	Rutaceae	T
246	<i>Maerua apetala</i> (Spreng.) M. Jacobs	Capparaceae	S
247	<i>Malachra capitata</i> (L.) L.	Malvaceae	H
248	<i>Malvastrum coromandelianum</i> (L.) Garcke	Malvaceae	H
249	<i>Martynia annua</i> L.	Martyniaceae	H
250	<i>Melanocenthris jacquemontii</i> Jaub. & Spach	Poaceae	H
251	<i>Melhania incana</i> B.Heyne ex Wall.	Malvaceae	H
252	<i>Melochia corchorifolia</i> L.	Malvaceae	H
253	<i>Merremia gangetica</i> Cufod.	Convolvulaceae	C
254	<i>Merremia tridentata</i> (L.) Hallier f.	Convolvulaceae	C

255	<i>Mimosa hamata</i> Willd	Fabaceae	S
256	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Fabaceae	H
257	<i>Mollugo nudicaulis</i> Lam	Molluginaceae	H
258	<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.	Molluginaceae	H
259	<i>Morinda pubescens</i> Sm.	Rubiaceae	T
260	<i>Mukia maderaspatana</i> (L.) M.Roem.	Cucurbitaceae	C
261	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	Lamiaceae	H
262	<i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	Rubiaceae	H
263	<i>Oldenlandia herbacea</i> (L.) Roxb	Rubiaceae	H
264	<i>Oldenlandia umbellata</i> L.	Rubiaceae	H
265	<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso	Convolvulaceae	C
266	<i>Opuntia stricta</i> (Haw.) Haw.	Cactaceae	S
267	<i>Orthosiphon rubicundus</i> (D.Don) Benth.	Lamiaceae	H
268	<i>Oxystelma esculentum</i> (L. f.) Sm.	Apocyanaceae	L
269	<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	H
270	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	Asteraceae	H
271	<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	H
272	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	H
273	<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	Passifloraceae	V
274	<i>Pavetta indica</i> L.	Rubiaceae	T
275	<i>Pavonia odorata</i> Willd	Malvaceae	S
276	<i>Pavonia zeylanica</i> (L.) Cav	Malvaceae	H
277	<i>Pedaliium murex</i> L.	Pedaliaceae	H
278	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling	Asteraceae	H
279	<i>Pentatropis capensis</i> (L. f.) Bullock	Apocyanaceae	Twin
280	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Apocyanaceae	C
281	<i>Perotis indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Poaceae	H
282	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb	Arecaceae	T
283	<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	Verbenaceae	H
284	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumach. & Thonn.	Phyllanthaceae	H
285	<i>Phyllanthus debilis</i> Klein ex Willd.	Phyllanthaceae	H
286	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	T
287	<i>Phyllanthus maderaspatensis</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	H
288	<i>Phyllanthus reticulatus</i> Poir.	Phyllanthaceae	S
289	<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> G.Forst.	Phyllanthaceae	H
290	<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Solanaceae	H
291	<i>Pigea enneasperma</i> (L.) P.I. Forst. (= <i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i> (L.) F.Muell.)	Violaceae	H
292	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth	Fabaceae	T
293	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Plumbaginaceae	H
294	<i>Polycarpaea aurea</i> Wight & Arn.	Caryophyllaceae	H
295	<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam	Caryophyllaceae	H
296	<i>Polygala arvensis</i> Willd.	Polygalaceae	H
297	<i>Polygala chinensis</i> L.	Polygalaceae	H
298	<i>Polygala elongata</i> Klein ex Willd.	Polygalaceae	H
299	<i>Polygala erioptera</i> DC	Polygalaceae	H
300	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Fabaceae	T
301	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Portulacaceae	H
302	<i>Portulaca quadrifida</i> L.	Portulacaceae	H
303	<i>Premna mollissima</i> Roth	Lamiaceae	S
304	<i>Premna tomentosa</i> Willd.	Lamiaceae	T
305	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce	Fabaceae	T
306	<i>Pterolobium hexapetalum</i> (Roth) Santapau & Wagh	Fabaceae	S
307	<i>Pulicaria wightiana</i> (DC.) C.B.Clarke	Asteraceae	H
308	<i>Pupalia lappacea</i> (L.) Juss.	Amaranthaceae	H
309	<i>Pycneus flavidus</i> (Retz.) T.Koyama	Cyperaceae	H
310	<i>Rhynchosia capitata</i> (Roth) DC	Fabaceae	C

311	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i> (L.) DC.	Fabaceae	H
312	<i>Rhynchosia suaveolens</i> (L.f.) DC	Fabaceae	S
313	<i>Rivea hypocrateriformis</i>	Convolvulaceae	c
314	<i>Rostellularia prostrata</i> (C.B.Clarke) R.B.Majumdar	Acanthaceae	H
315	<i>Ruellia patula</i> Jacq	Acanthaceae	H
316	<i>Rungia pectinata</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
317	<i>Rungia repens</i> (L.) Nees	Acanthaceae	H
318	<i>Sapindus emarginatus</i> Vahl	Sapindaceae	T
319	<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Apocyanaceae	Twin
320	<i>Senna auriculata</i> (L.) Roxb	Fabaceae	S
321	<i>Senna italica</i> Mill	Fabaceae	H
322	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	Fabaceae	S
323	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb	Fabaceae	H
324	<i>Sesamum alatum</i> Thonn	Pedaliaceae	H
325	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L	Pedaliaceae	H
326	<i>Setaria intermedia</i> Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
327	<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.	Poaceae	H
328	<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) P.Beauv.	Poaceae	H
329	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	Malvaceae	H
330	<i>Sida cordata</i> (Burm.f.) Borss.Waalk	Malvaceae	H
331	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L	Malvaceae	H
332	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L	Malvaceae	H
333	<i>Sida spinosa</i> L	Malvaceae	H
334	<i>Smithia conferta</i> Sm	Fabaceae	H
335	<i>Solanum anguivi</i> Lam	Solanaceae	S
336	<i>Solanum pubescence</i> Willd	Solanaceae	S
337	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm. f.	Solanaceae	H
338	<i>Solanum trilobatum</i> L.	Solanaceae	S
339	<i>Spermacoce articularis</i> L.f.	Rubiaceae	H
340	<i>Spermacoce pusilla</i> Wall.	Rubiaceae	H
341	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Asteraceae	H
342	<i>Sporobolus coromandelianus</i> (Retz.) Kunth	Poaceae	H
343	<i>Stachytarpheta jamaicensis</i> (L.) Vahl	Verbenaceae	H
344	<i>Striga asiatica</i> (L.) Kuntze	Orobanchaceae	H
345	<i>Stylosanthes fruticosa</i> (Retz.) Alston	Fabaceae	H
346	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	T
347	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L	Fabaceae	T
348	<i>Tephrosia maxima</i> (L.) Pers	Fabaceae	H
349	<i>Tephrosia pumila</i> (Lam.) Pers.	Fabaceae	H
350	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	Fabaceae	H
351	<i>Tephrosia strigosa</i> (Dalzell) Santapau & Maheshw.	Fabaceae	H
352	<i>Tephrosia villosa</i> (L.) Pers.	Fabaceae	H
353	<i>Tetrapogon tenellus</i> (Roxb.) Chiov	Poaceae	H
354	<i>Tinopora sinensis</i>	Menispermaceae	C
355	<i>Tragus mongolorum</i> Ohwi	Poaceae	H
356	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i>	Aizoaceae	h
357	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L	Zygophyllaceae	H
358	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Lehm.	Boraginaceae	H
359	<i>Trichodesma zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) R.Br	Boraginaceae	H
360	<i>Trichuriella monsoniae</i> (L. f.) Bennet	Amaranthaceae	H
361	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	H
362	<i>Triumfetta pentandra</i> A.Rich	Malvaceae	H
363	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i> Jacq	Malvaceae	H
364	<i>Triumfetta rotundifolia</i> Lam	Malvaceae	H
365	<i>Urena lobata</i> L	Malvaceae	H
366	<i>Ventilago maderaspatana</i> Gaertn.	Rhamnaceae	C
367	<i>Vigna aconitifolia</i> (Jacq.) Marechal	Fabaceae	H

368	<i>Vigna trilobata</i> (L.) Verdc.	Fabaceae	H
369	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Lamiaceae	S
370	<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.	Malvaceae	S
371	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> R.Br.	Apocyanaceae	T
372	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	S
373	<i>Zaleya decandra</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Aizoaceae	H
374	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill	Rhamnaceae	T
375	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (L.) Mill	Rhamnaceae	S
376	<i>Ziziphus rugosa</i> Lam	Rhamnaceae	T
377	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd.	Rhamnaceae	T
378	<i>Zornia gibbosa</i> Span.	Fabaceae	H

